

Extended data for manuscript: CIViCutils: matching and downstream processing of clinical annotations from CIViC

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EXTENDED DATA

1. Sample-level matches

The number of input SNVs available per patient in the TCGA-BLCA cohort spanned from 0 to 574 across patients, with an overall mean of 33 SNVs, whereas the average number of CNVs was 50, ranging between 0 and 243. Two samples showed no targetable SNVs or CNVs, and one sample did not show CNVs. We computed the fraction and absolute number of variants found in CIViC for every subject in the TCGA-BLCA dataset. While all samples with CNVs could be linked to one or more knowledgebase records, there were seven for which none of their SNVs could be successfully matched. As illustrated in [Figure S1](#), CIViCutils could retrieve clinical information for 23% of the SNVs detected per patient on average, showing a range from 0% to 75%. CNVs associated with CIViC data varied between 0% and 100% of the available alterations depending on the tumor, with 78.7% of CNVs being matched on average. In addition, we evaluated the mean number of CIViC variant records retrieved per single input aberration (excluding those without a match in CIViC), estimated separately at the sample level and averaged across all subjects. Here, on average two hits were identified per SNV and one hit per CNV.

Supplementary Figure 1. SNVs vs. CNVs matching to CIViC information. Boxplots illustrate the distribution of variant fractions with CIViC information available across individual TCGA-BLCA samples, separated by type of genomic alteration. Each data point (not shown) represents the proportion of aberrations from one bladder cancer sample which could be matched in CIViC, relative to their total number of variants available.

2. Tier-based matching of variants

We further summarized the distribution of the tier-based hits reported by CIViCutils after linking CIViC evidence to the molecular aberrations. Note that only the highest tier category found per input variant was selected by our pipeline (hierarchical order: tier 1 > tier 1b > tier 2 > tier 3).

The proportion and absolute number of tier matches were assessed at the patient level throughout the entire TCGA-BLCA cohort. We determined that on average per sample 26 SNVs and 13 CNVs classified as tier 4 variants (i.e. they could not be matched in CIViC), SNVs ranging from 0 to 486 and CNVs ranging from 0 to 138. This translates into roughly 76.2% of SNVs and 20.6% of CNVs being classified as tier 4 for every tumor. [Figure S2](#) illustrates the percentages of the remaining tiers per sample. On average, CIViCutils could assign 11% of the matched SNVs per tumor as tier 1, 46% as tier 1b, and 41% as tier 3. Tier 2 SNVs were rarely identified (average 0.2%). For CNVs more variants classified as tier 1 compared to the SNVs: per sample on average 44% of the CNVs linked to CIViC records were tier 1. Also for CNVs tier 2 was rarely classified (0.4%), whereas with 55% the percentage of tier 3 variants was even higher than for SNVs.

Supplementary Figure 2. Tier-based categories reported across the TCGA-BLCA cohort (tier 1 > 1b > 2 > 3). Boxplots depict the distribution of patient-based tier fractions which could be linked to CIViC evidence, evaluated separately for SNVs (top) and CNVs (bottom). Each data point represents the proportion of a given tier observed in one bladder cancer sample, thus, the sum of percentages across tiers should be 100% for the same patient and type of genomic alteration.

3. CIViC evidence

We evaluated the distribution of the clinical data gathered from CIViC for the set of 18,056 TCGA-BLCA variants matched by CIViCutils, in terms of associated evidence type as defined in the knowledgebase (“Predictive”, “Prognostic”, “Diagnostic”, Predisposing”; see Fig. S3). For each patient, we counted the number of SNVs and CNVs that were linked to at least one predictive, prognostic, diagnostic or predisposing CIViC record. Note that in situations where multiple evidence items of different types were available for the same cancer aberration, we simultaneously included the variant in the counts of all evidence types encountered for the subject. We found that, on average, CIViCutils annotated 5 SNVs and 17 CNVs per tumor with one or more predictive evidence records, with single values ranging from 0 to 63 for SNVs and from 0 to 38 for CNVs. For prognostic records, both SNVs and CNVs showed a range from 0 to 17 associated variants in the cohort samples, however, the average number of occurrences per sample was higher in CNVs (average 9) compared to SNVs (average 2). The variant counts linked with diagnostic evidence were considerably lower, spanning from 0 to 8 for SNVs (average < 1) and from 0 to 3 for CNVs (average 1), whereas CIViCutils reported no hits having predisposing evidence available across the entire TCGA-BLCA dataset, regardless of the type of aberration at hand.

Likewise, we also kept track of the number of non-tier 3 SNVs and CNVs per patient associated with predictive, prognostic, diagnostic and predisposing evidence. The purpose behind tier 3 matches is to facilitate manual curation of all clinical data available for the corresponding gene, whenever no suitable record could be matched in CIViC. Since in tier 3 all variant records that could be obtained from CIViC for the gene and type of genomic alteration at hand (if any) are returned, the set of

retrieved evidence items often corresponds to a heterogenous aggregation of data from multiple CIViC variants. To analyze the effect of tier 3 hits on the landscape of CIViC record types, we repeated the counting of cancer aberrations for each sample and evidence type, this time without including those identified as tier 3. As represented in [Figure S3](#), in general, slightly smaller variant counts were observed after excluding tier 3 hits, spanning narrower intervals with lower upper limits throughout the cohort. However, the average numbers across the bladder cancer patients were comparable for all types of evidence.

Supplementary Figure 3. Predictive evidence accounts for the majority of the CIViC information extracted by CIViCutils. Boxplots illustrate the distribution of the TCGA-BLCA SNVs and CNVs per type of associated CIViC evidence, before and after excluding tier 3 variants. Note that the depicted y-axes are scaled differently for SNVs and CNVs.

Independently of the type of genomic alteration being analyzed, predictive evidence records were the most frequently reported by CIViCutils across TCGA-BLCA variants, followed by prognostic information, while diagnostic evidence was found to be scarce, and no predisposing records could be retrieved for any patient in the entire cohort. The bias toward evidence claims of treatment response in the knowledgebase has already been described in Griffith et al.¹.

¹ Griffith M, Spies NC, Krysiak K, McMichael JF, Coffman AC, Danos AM, et al. CIViC is a community knowledgebase for expert crowdsourcing the clinical interpretation of variants in cancer. *Nat Genet.* 2017 Jan 31;49(2):170–4. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/ng.3774>

4. NCT disease types and CT and GT hits for SNVs and CNVs

After assigning the retrieved CIViC records into ct, gt, and nct according to their disease specificity, 91% of the SNV-based disease names available per tumor were identified as nct by CIViCutils, which translated into on average 13 separate nct indications being assigned for each sample, ranging between 0 and 55 different cancer types, depending on the patient. In comparison, ct indications associated with SNVs were significantly scarcer (mean 5%) and three ct labels were annotated at most within the same sample. Furthermore, we observed a larger average proportion (94%) of nct cancers per subject in the CNV dataset. Also, and similarly as with the number of diseases available for each sample, the nct count based on CNVs was remarkably larger than that of the SNVs (mean 27), varying between 0 and 47 nct cancers across the data. In addition, a smaller average fraction (3%) of ct indications linked with CNVs was found compared to the SNV set. In terms of absolute counts, CIViCutils classified at most one ct indication within the same tumor sample. On the other hand, gt cancers were even more sparsely reported in the cohort than ct ones, both for SNVs (mean 0.1) and for CNVs (mean 0.6), and the highest number of gt disease names annotated per sample was 1 for both variant types. We credit the low frequencies associated with ct and gt indications in the context of bladder cancer to the fact that CIViC contains just a handful of disease names fulfilling the conditions to be classified as such. In our use case, "bladder carcinoma", "invasive bladder transitional cell carcinoma", and "urinary bladder cancer" were matched as ct (in the case of CNVs, solely the first one was available), whereas the only gt indication found was "solid tumor".

5. Consensus drug response predictions

[Figure S4](#) illustrates the overall percentage of variants with consensus drug response predictions observed throughout the TCGA-BLCA cohort per type of molecular aberration. After aggregating drug-related variants across the 412 patients, we obtained predictions for 73.5% (n=2,105) of all SNVs that were matched in CIViC, leaving only 26.5% (n=759) where treatment information could not be retrieved. For CNVs, consensus therapies were identified for only 46% (n=6,972), leaving 54% (n=8,220) without a possible prediction. Notably, the proportion of genomic alterations linked to treatment predictions increased when excluding tier 3 matches, reaching comparable fractions of drug-related SNVs (91%, n=1,386) and CNVs (92%, n=5,451), and leading to only 9% (n=138) SNVs and 8% (n=461) CNVs where unanimous drug data was not available.

Supplementary Figure 4. Distributions of SNVs and CNVs associated with consensus drugs. Pie charts show the overall fraction of TCGA-BLCA variants with one or more unanimous treatments reported by CIViCutils. Molecular alterations which could not be associated with any drug predictions are represented in gray.

Moreover, we annotated all TCGA-BLCA variants that have predictive evidence with disease-specific consensus drug response predictions. Through this feature, actionable molecular alterations can be targeted with promising therapies tailored not only to a particular patient but also to a specific cancer subtype. We could retrieve CIViC drug information for 96% of the TCGA-BLCA samples having actionable SNVs, while this percentage was 100% in the case of CNVs. The mean fraction of consensus predictions generated per cancer aberration and treatment response (i.e. "SUPPORT", "RESISTANCE", "CONFLICT", "UNKNOWN") was computed for every TCGA-BLCA patient, before and after tier 3 hits were removed (see [Fig. S6](#)). Per sample, the number of all variants with predictive evidence was averaged based on all the drug-related aberrations. The majority of treatment predictions were assigned category "SUPPORT", observing equivalent distributions throughout the cohort for both types of molecular alterations. On average, per sample "SUPPORT" accounted for 68% and 65% of the unanimous responses available for each drug-related SNV and CNV, respectively. The second most prevalent prediction was "RESISTANCE", typically representing 22% of the SNV-related entries and 24% of the CNV-related entries. The proportion of category "RESISTANCE" observed at the variant level for SNVs spanned between 0% and 100% across individual bladder cancer patients, whereas the CNV interval varied from 0% to 51%. This indicates that for CNVs "RESISTANCE" was always reported together with another response associated to different treatments and/or cancer specificities (but still with type "RESISTANCE", otherwise the consensus prediction would have been "CONFLICT", due to the presence of contradicting information). Categories "UNKNOWN" and "CONFLICT" were only rarely annotated throughout the entire TCGA-BLCA cohort. "UNKNOWN" was on average assigned for 4% of the SNVs and 11% of CNVs. "CONFLICT" was very rare, irrespective of the type of cancer aberration being evaluated or

whether tier 3 matches were present or not. On average, this drug response accounted for only 0.7% of the predictions retrieved for the SNVs and 0.1% of the predictions retrieved for each CNV per sample.

Supplementary Figure 5. Average number of consensus predictions annotated for SNVs and CNVs. Boxplots illustrate the mean number of consensus drug response predictions reported per variant for every patient in the TCGA-BLCA cohort. Each data point (only outliers shown) derives from averaging the total number of unanimous predictions observed for one bladder cancer sample, relative to the total number of tumor aberrations where CIViCutils could report consensus information. Data were evaluated separately for SNVs and CNVs, before and after tier 3 matches were removed.

Supplementary Figure 6. Consensus drug responses throughout the TCGA-BLCA cohort. Boxplots show the mean fraction of unanimous predictions available per cancer variant for every subject in the cohort, according to the type of therapy response annotated ("SUPPORT", "RESISTANCE", "CONFLICT", "UNKNOWN") based on the underlying predictive evidence from CIVIC. Each data point (only outliers represented) results from averaging the relative proportions of treatment entries observed per molecular alteration across all the drug-related aberrations in one bladder cancer patient, before and after tier 3 hits were excluded.